

CHALLENGES FOR THE OCEAN

Trends Toward a New Environmental Era for the Oceans

Proposal

Artur Victoria, MS

Maria Helena Fonseca de Souza Rolim, Ph.D

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PROJECT AUTHORS - COORDINATORS

Professor Maria Helena Fonseca de Souza Rolim, Ph.D

Professor Artur Victoria, MS

SOAMAR Portugal, President

RESEARCHERS – CONSULTANTS

André Luiz Pierre Mattei, Dr. Eng., Cel (Ret.)

Senai Innovation Institute for Embedded Systems, Chief Science Officer - BRAZIL

Rubens Barbosa, Ambassador

Institute of International Relations and Foreign Trade - IRICE, President, Brazil

Victor Alencar Mayer Feitosa Ventura, Ph.D

Marcus Vinicius De Freitas, LL.M and LL.B

Visiting Professor, China Foreign Affairs University

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Forewords

Pericles once affirmed *“He who rules the seas rules the world”*. This statement has been considered a reality in global governance. From the past until now, though it may seem less relevant, with the increased importance of space technology, the argument still holds. The seas still remain the fundamental venue for trade, economic growth, natural resources, wealth and military mobility. With power slowly shifting from the Atlantic to the Pacific Ocean, where most of the world’s population is concentrated, the need for revival of the Atlantic is essential for its continued relevance.

The Atlantic Ocean, whose margins separated between 175 and 90 million years ago, is the youngest of the world oceans. Its margins are the cradle where most of international trade has taken place throughout modern history. Lately, it has also been the new frontier of developments in economic exploration of natural resources.

Currently, the Atlantic is at a crossroads moment - There is a coastal State dependency on the ocean, since 90% of trade is conducted through sea routes. The maritimisation of the Wider Atlantic economies has gained strength, as coastlines have expanded their role in the production of national wealth, resulting from trade, hydrocarbon resources, fisheries, heavy industries and ever expanding coastal cities. Nevertheless, the increasing and spread of the negative impact of these activities on the Triangle Atlantic marine environment as well as on safety and security evokes policies to address such dependencies, revise national and international law on the issue and review the possible disputes and claims. This is particularly true in Africa, where there are growing disputes over maritime delimitation, which may lead to the escalation of maritime conflicts, despite UNCLOS regulations. Yet UNCLOS also faces some controversies regarding its interpretation and application.

Challenges for the ocean: Trends Toward a New Environmental Era for the Oceans (The Project) acknowledge that Wider Atlantic nations have been taking ownership of the challenges with a steady effort to control its destiny, through resilience, cooperation and institutionalization. Accordingly, the Project presents tools to the countries to face the legal aspects of sustainable development and geopolitical challenges which can be developed accordingly the sponsor interest or adapt to the local priorities. Moreover, it is possible to sponsor and implement separately each topics of the Project.

The Project may be adopted through the Maritime Sustainability Network (MSN), which has a flexibility that allows Academic entities to join the Network either in

individual or in partnership and having options on the great areas of research accordingly their own conveniences and Research Centres. *See Appendix A.*

The Project is based on four key issues: *(1) Environmental Protection: Ballast Water and Ocean Acidification/ Climate Change; (2) Fisheries; (3) Law of the Sea/Space Law: Interaction Aiming to Protect the Oceans (Appendix B) and (4) Good Order at Sea: Maritime Safety and Security Challenges in the Atlantic Triangle. See Appendixes B and C.*

Maritime cooperation among countries in the Atlantic is the general philosophy, which underlies this Project. Nevertheless, the Project may be applied/extended to the “countries of network” referred below. The revision of the gaps in international environmental law of the sea and environmental –related instruments towards a more sustainable World by using education, training, dissemination of information and research is the leitmotiv of the Project.

1. Introduction

This Project proposes to improve knowledge and awareness regarding the Atlantic Ocean via training and information availability. It intends to improve the individual and collective understanding of the importance of the sea to the nations via both training and stimulating the development of behaviors to use the potential of the sea and waterways in a sustainable way. To achieve its purposes, the Project will disseminate and promote scientific and educational activities in the educational institutions of the Atlantic countries, offering opportunities for participation to the academy and institutions dedicated to these matters and introduce courses, conferences, lectures, legal adviser and students orientation regarding the Specifics Objectives bellow mentioned.

Results are expected with the implementation of the project:

- In the Academia it contributes to the greater formalization of scientific and technological activities at the Academy, generating a framed actions of specific courses, lectures, seminars, congresses and research;
- In Governments a partner institution for evaluating and revising national and international Law as well provides courses for public servants working in this area;
- In the Private or public/private industrial and commercial sector connected to the naval industry, provides a peer of contacts network through the MSI and shared knowledge to improve their production and sells;
- Cooperation between institutions and schools is also expected to be strengthened. It is intended to strengthen the capacity to participate and be the promoter of innovation actions;
- Reinforce the group of people interested in the Sea and Maritime Mentality who seek, promote and participate as an actor in professional activities and educational training. As indicators of control, we will have the number of individuals who communicate and access to the data query inserted and, on the other hand, the participants in colloquiums, Workshops and exhibitions Itinerant for Young people.

a. Spatial Scope

The spatial scope of this project is variable depending on whether the action is more extensive in the case of compilation and processing of new data, where it is intended to cover the countries bordering the Atlantic Triangle and more restricted in the institutions that offer the ideal conditions for hosting the activities.

b. Systematization

The intervention methodologies, budgets, technical and human means, timetable and institutions involved are elements that vary according to the action considered and will be addressed in their specificity in annexed tabulations (which characterize each of the actions). It should be noted, however, that the methodologies used will always privilege the interconnection Environment/ Sustainability and Legal Aspects.

c. Law and Technology

The technology development has required the law to respond. Indeed, law never seeks to regulate technology, but rather aims to place order on the competing human interests that results from that technology. The impact of new technologies on the evolution of the international law is, particularly, connected with the law of the sea and in general with space law.

Considering the ocean problems evokes an holistic perspective to achieve sustainable development, the purpose of this Project is to link the rule of Law to scientific and technology challenges to reduce the impact of the exchange and the discharge of ballast water on the oceans; to minimize the impact of climate change on the marine environment; to promote a competitive fishery *vis-a-vis* a sustainable environment; to understand space technology/ policy/ legal framework as an essential tool to protect the oceans; and to guide toward a good order at sea.

d. The Need of this Project

Confidence building measures seems to work best from the bottom-up, through concrete achievements. Initiatives fostering tangible cooperation and the emergence of the Atlantic issues-based networks of experts and professionals can surely help to pave the way towards more cooperation. The main task will be to get in touch with these experts and establish with them the desirable networking.

In this sense, efforts may be directed initially towards cooperation in the fields of education and training (which includes education, training, capacity building and operation of forces); sharing knowledge, best practices and experiences at different levels and the pooling of means and technologies.

The peace experienced by the Atlantic is an invaluable regional heritage for the stability and development of the Atlantic countries. Its preservation for the next generations depends, however, on our ability to establish, improve and consolidate regional mechanisms of trust, coordination and cooperation

Actually, the sea affairs has a hypercluster characteristic and shall be addressed in articulation with several aspects with respect to the issue, i.e., national and international juridical framework regarding environmental law of the sea; fisheries; ports; maritime transportation; off shore resources; territorial delimitation, in particular the legal regime to the EEZ; and ocean safety and security.

The Project identifies that the sea is essential for countries development, considering the unexplored huge potential in the economic, scientific research and defense and security matters. These issues evoke a holistic perspective to solve the challenges pose by new maritime strategic era.

2. Objectives

2.1. General Objective

To increase the current level of environmental protection, safety, and security to the Atlantic Ocean by providing modern training and regulations review. The main purpose of *Triangle Atlantic Project* is to achieve the sustainability of the Atlantic Ocean based on four (4) essential pillars:

- a. Sustainability;
- b. Legal protection of the marine ecosystem and environment;
- c. Sea routes security;
- d. Natural resources control *vis-a-vis* economic development and population welfare

2.2. Specific Objectives

Training activities

- a. Applied courses for university, students and public administrators regarding the matters referred in Appendixes B and C;
- b. Both short and specialized courses aiming professional skills development regarding the matters referred in Appendixes B and C;
- c. Workshops and Symposiums regarding the matters referred in Appendixes B and C;
- d. Evaluation of public policies and inherent reforms.
- e. "Tailored" courses accordingly specific institutional needs.

Regulations review

The Academy may improve the elaboration, construction and adviser with respect to the matters referred in Appendixes B and C.

- a. Legislative Revision: effective regulatory design in a time of change;
- b. Environmental Law of the Sea and Policy: Ballast Water handling; Ocean Acidity and Climate Change;
- c. Law of the Sea: Fisheries;
- d. Space Law interconnected with the Law of the Sea: Interaction aiming to Protect the Oceans;
- e. Maritime Safety and Security: Strategic Maintenance of peace on the Atlantic Triangle;

Countries of the Network

The Project is mainly addressed to the following countries, namely;

- a. In Europe: Portugal and Spain;
- b. In South America: Brazil and Argentina;

- c. In West Africa: Cape Verde and Guinea-Bissau;**
- d. In Central Africa: Sao Tome and Principe, Gabon, Republic of Congo and Democratic Republic of Congo;**
- e. In Southern Africa: Angola, Zambia, Mozambique, Namibia, Zimbabwe and South Africa.**
- f. Non Atlantic Countries that use the Atlantic as part of their maritime routes**

3. Project Scope

Two subprojects integrate this proposal to achieve its scope:

- a. **Specialized training;**
- b. **Regulatory consulting;**

3.1. Specialized training

- a. **Academia:** Annual and Summer Courses and Degrees (MS and PhDs.), Research, Workshops;
- b. **Government:** Analysis of legislation, analysis of Analytical results of current legislation, enforcing legislation process and consultancy;
- c. **Public/Private institutions:** Seminars, international meetings, consultancy and innovation projects follow up.

3.2. Regulatory consulting

a. Policy Development:

- . Roles and Responsibilities
- . Development and Dissemination of Legal Compliance Policy
- . Revision of the Policy Development Process
- . Development of Internal Rules and Organizational Frameworks
- . Development and Dissemination of Internal Rules
- . Establishment of System of the Compliance Control Division
- . Development of Legal Compliance System in Operation Divisions
- . Development and Dissemination of Compliance Manual
- . Development and Dissemination of Compliance Program
- . Development of Internal Audit Guidelines and Internal Audit Plan
- . Revision of Development Process of Internal Rules and Organizational Frameworks

b. Assessment and Improvement Activities

- . Analysis and Assessment
- . Analysis and Assessment of Legal Compliance System
- . Revision of Analysis and Assessment Processes
- . Improvement Activities
- . Implementation of Improvements

Appendix A: Maritime Sustainability Network (MSN)

1. Introduction

Considering the ocean problems evokes an holistic perspective to achieve sustainable development, to minimize the impact of climate change on marine ecosystem and to preserve the marine environment, the purpose of this Project is to link the rule of Law to scientific and technology challenges.

Sustainability of the Atlantic Ocean – and a procedural unit – intervention based on two essential pillars: Sustainability and Technology - are the core of the Project.

In order to contribute to this academic process the **Maritime Sustainability Network (MSN)** was established in 2018. MSN seeks to implement the vision through a quiet yet radical review of what constitutes useful knowledge to serve as the basis of skills and capacity raising courses. Rather than taking the top-down, generalizing, supply of expertise model, MSN has developed a network learning organization in which double loop learning is applied, to ensure a rapid adaptation to needs. Furthermore, MSN seeks to service this network rather than dictate to it, creating partnerships rather than interventions.

Since its establishment, MSN has developed an approach that enables the development of networks, new types of knowledge and new means of disseminating it. It has also pioneered online forums in which otherwise dispersed groups and individuals can collaborate to produce and adapt knowledge of what can and should be taught to support pro-Ocean Atlantic sustainability.

This development phase has resulted in a network of Africa (mainly in developing countries) and over Brazil and Europe.

MSN has created new knowledge about the process and is actively bringing practitioner experience into a form appropriate to use in an academic setting. This is being done with a number of organizations. MSN has produced perhaps the most extensive resource from Law to scientific and technology. MSN is also developing specific search tools to support the access and systematization of knowledge in this field.

The breadth and growth of MSN has been a consequence of demand. This rapid growth has left identified areas that need strengthening and extending if it is to meet its objective of making applied skills into a mainstream educational option. MSN needs to be able to focus closely on its clients and the core service it delivers. This requires improved communication and services and resources. It also needs to expand into regions in which for lack of resources it has not been able to initiate activity.

In order to benefit from the economies of scale in the MSN model and to overcome identified capacity constraints within the networks, strategic re-granting is planned to complement the program activities developed to date. This model will provide the means of achieving a situation in which within three years those wishing to gain pro-sustainability skills will be able to do 50 in SO% of countries in which have coasts to the Oceans. Within ten years MSN will help to make Oceans Studies part of the teaching and research mainstream.

2. Need for MSN

Over the last 25 years, a compelling body of evidence has been accumulated concerning the harm and waste caused by oceans pollution and low levels of public policies. The sums estimated are vast. The impact fall is disproportionately on developing countries and on the poor within these countries. Flows of aid and structural lending remains significant to many developing countries are significant in terms of GNP.

Aid and the development it is intended to spur is, however, often caught in a negative relationship, in which aid can fuel negative outcomes through its impact on ocean pollution and illegal fishery. It is largely against this background that a civil society and donor movement to support oceans sustainability and establish high levels of public concern has evolved.

This pro-maritime natural resources reform movement has undergone three major phases in its recent history: the first being awareness raising, the second the creation of conventions and international legislative structures and the third, in which we are now situated where implementation and enforcement are the overriding imperatives.

Despite the diligent efforts of many committed people reform successes remain relatively few and far between, either they are relatively distant historically (the changes in Northern Europe one and two hundred year's age). There is widespread uncertainty about whether the way achieves improvement in public concern and action is currently well understood, even if many of the attributes of high levels of maritime pollution are increasingly clear. The historically favored strategy of implementing international 'best practice' has overwhelmingly been a failure. Implementing public maritime reform is a considerable strategic public management challenge that requires the mobilization of large numbers of skilled people and resources to succeed.

Currently there is a highly dispersed set of experiences and practices, both in the research and practice domains. A large and relatively unsystematic body of knowledge has been built up. The reliable application of this knowledge in practice

remains at an embryonic stage if we are to judge by changes in governance over time.

Despite the concept of Maritime Sustainability gaining common currency in the popular consciousness of most countries, as never before, it remains striking that within the academic community research and teaching remain dispersed, with very few courses being offered to meet the huge challenge of providing skills to support the Natural Maritime resources use reform process.

At present, much of the knowledge creation and impetus for Maritime Sustainability reform is coming largely from international organizations, be they donors or NGO's. These organizations have initiated or provided the knowledge for many of the reforms that have been attempted (World Bank, UN and so forth).

This 'supply' model has some strength in that it has been able to develop a high quality of material, and a critical set of methodologies. The resources required to 'deliver' high levels of Maritime Sustainability in this way are huge though, even if it were possible; arguably greater than the resources one could imagine being available.

This is due to the high costs of achieving:

- Strategic 'dosing' (prioritization/sequencing)
- Local legitimacy (policies come with ideological baggage)
- High quality of knowledge to transfer (Le. appropriateness to context)
- Local commitment or 'buy-in'

All these play a significant role in the application of Maritime Sustainability reforms and are hard to overcome when applying a top-down, internationally driven approach to Maritime Sustainability reform, such as has characterized much policy to date.

Reformers then face the challenge providing high quality knowledge to a large number of people in a sustainable manner to achieve their objectives. Despite the increasingly clear evidence of social benefits from high Maritime Sustainability the capacity pre-requisites have delivered very little that is developed and sustained within local education and training sectors.

The purpose of the Maritime Sustainability Network (MSN) is to meet this challenge and to overcome these persistent impediments to pro- Maritime Sustainability reform:

1. Unsystematic knowledge

- 2. Poor quality or poorly adapted knowledge**
- 3. Lack of applied knowledge**
- 4. Dispersed expertise**
- 5. Lack of sustainable dissemination of knowledge**

The MSN provides a framework for the best of international (codified) knowledge to be blended with the tacit or experience based knowledge of local actors to raise capacities that will advance pro- Maritime Sustainability reform in countries on a case-by-case basis.

3. Measurability

MSN works in an area of Maritime Sustainability reform that has traditionally been resistant to attempts at measurement of the quality and effectiveness of its activity. Outputs are often measured only in terms of the program logic itself or in vague terms. Part of this is due to the complexity and cost of measuring the impact of capacity raising initiatives, part perhaps a negative incentive not to address the issue for many apparently good reasons.

MSN's activity is developed from an analysis of the reform agenda that asserts that more knowledge needs to be disseminated in order to advance the reform agenda globally. In order to do this codified knowledge must be fused with tacit knowledge and appropriated and developed by the communities seeking reform. This approach is consistent with the underlying approach that knowledge rather than information needs to be disseminated to support pro- Maritime Sustainability reform.

It is not practical to show indicators of MSN's own effectiveness on the levels of Maritime Sustainability or reform in a given country. The causal links are too blurred for this to be possible. What MSN can do is to base an assessment of its performance based on the logic of its activities and the extent to which its activities are consistent with that logic and are measurable in outputs. Indicators also have to be methodologically meaningful and practically realizable.

The Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for MSN and our network partners are the cases of the Application of knowledge and skills to make Maritime Sustainability work in defined settings. As an organization concerned with knowledge management indicators of MSN work need to answer some key questions concerning its activities and the impact they have on knowledge:

1. What is the degree of the MSN's activity? Has MSN been active in the number of projects it has initiated? What has been the activity in terms of end-user outputs of its projects? How widely have the results of the activities been disseminated?

2 . What is the quality of the knowledge generated by MSN's activities? To what extent is the process of developing knowledge from information and the blending of tacit and codified knowledge achieved through MSN's activities?

3. What is the sustainability of the knowledge management process? How well has the transition to local ownership been achieved, which is also a good indicator of demand? Is the process shallow or deep (Le. what sort of network and organizations are supporting the initiative locally)?

The measurable indicators are the following:

Quantity	Quality	Sustainability
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of partners. • # of partners from new post-war reconstruction settings. • # of courses developed (in-country and stand alone). • # of scholarships attributed. • # of policy papers co-ordinated. • # of commissioned papers. • # of countries of activity. • # of dissemination activities and resources. • # of users of the website. • # of replications, adaptations of MSN courses. • # of websites referencing Tiri and containing MSN materials. • # of partnership organizations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of codified sources employed. • # of types of codified sources employed. • # of tacit sources of knowledge introduced. • # of new sources of tacit and codified knowledge created. • # of institutions of high standing seeking MSN's assistance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of organizations involved. • Range of engaged actors and organizations. • Declining long term input from MSN. • Knowledge retention in MSN. • Local sources of funding. • Double loop learning in practice. • Influence on policy.

None of these indicators are sufficient in themselves. But together they represent a coherent response to the motivation for the organization and thus a satisfactory goal for the development of an index.

Appendix B: Law of the Sea and Policy

The oceans and coastlines are vital for the planet and their resources and ecosystems need to be preserved. Industries such as shipping, tourism, and oil and gas depend on a sustainable development of the marine environment. Space technologies provide services and solutions that enable sustainable growth for the maritime environment. Satellite capabilities facilitate the understanding of both the challenges and the possible solutions. Satellites are then essential to provide surveillance services, environmental data, and remote areas connectivity to support sustainable economic activity as well as the protection of marine habitats. Taking into account the importance of space for human activities on the oceans, this Appendix provides an analysis of the congruence of the laws of these two areas.

1. Environmental Protection

1.1. Ballast Water

Justification

The uptake and discharge of ship's ballast water is potentially the most significant form of introducing invasive species in port and States' jurisdictions worldwide. Such discharges into the waters of port States may cause irreversible damage to the marine environment. Not only water is carried in the ballast tanks, but also an entire community of organisms, from viruses and bacteria to microscopic algae, spores of macroalgae, larvae, and adults of invertebrate animals, and even fish. There are thousands of examples of species introductions from all continents. In general, all ecosystems are open to bioinvasion. These alien invasive species have had deleterious effects not only on native species and ecosystem functions, but also on fishing and aquaculture industries, on commercially important native species, and consequently on economies of the riparian countries, as well as human health. They continue to grow at an alarming pace.

International shipping has been identified as one of the key pathways for the movement of species between differing ecosystems. Shipping is an international industry that requires harmonized standards and States have an international obligation to cooperate in developing and implementing international standards. Failure to recognize the international dimension of this problem and the importance of cooperative efforts by both flag and coastal States will result in non-compliance and conflict and will undermine the process of globally integrated ocean environmental protection and sustainable development. The alternatives, ships' operations based methods to address the problem on a precautionary basis, are not

fully satisfactory in the long term from a number of perspectives, including human safety.

It is essential to keep in mind a basic difference between bioinvasions (biological pollution) and other forms of marine pollution. While chemical and physical pollution can be reduced or stopped, living organisms tend to reproduce and spread if they meet hospitable environmental conditions in the water body into which they were initially released through shipping or other vectors. Scientists acknowledge that the oceans' natural communities are being disrupted by bioinvasions that are fast becoming one of the greatest threats to the Earth's biological diversity. This global problem underlies major ecological and economic negative impacts in numerous ecosystems.

The Atlantic Ocean, particularly, has been seriously affected by the deleterious effects of biological invasions of non-indigenous species, i.e., alien invasive species (see the Brazilian case, Annex 1). The challenges posed by the intense and increase growth of maritime transportation (see Annex 2), is interconnected, inter alia, with the increase of cargo volumes, bigger ships (= more ballast water to be transferred), faster ships (=better survival during the voyage), new donor and receiving areas (= new ship-assisted invasion corridors), as well as increased hull fouling due to the TBT (tributyltin) ban if effective new hull coatings is not available soon. High-risks areas are ports and waterways due to repeated releases of ballast water; dockyards due to emptying of ballast tanks sediments and cleaning of hull fouling; receiving waters for cooling water from power plants due to increased water temperature, hospitable for invaders native to lower latitudes and designated areas for ballast water exchange. One of the most critical (current or potential) contributors to changes in marine biodiversity is now acknowledged to be, *inter alia*, the invasion of exotic species.

The sensitivity to risk and the level of risk aversion required varies between countries and marine ecosystems combined with the fact that most countries are not in a position to identify the organisms in their waters that they may be exporting adds a further dimension to the problem, as a matter of administrative cost and attribution of liability. The IMO GloBallast Legislative Review endorses this teleology. Eradication of established alien invasive species is not a realistic option. Effective treatment methods for the control and management of ships ballast water to prevent or reduce the risks of ships-mediated introduction are required.

Satellite capabilities may support operational efficiency and monitoring of the environmental impact of ports (e.g., Ballast water), including end-to-end container tracking, scheduling and connectivity. Satellite services (remote sensing and data relay) provide coastal monitoring, protection, and environmental impact assessment, allowing sustainable economic growth.

Proposal

The central pillar of the international legal framework on the legal protection of the marine environment to avoid biopollution is the 2004 International Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast Water and Sediments (BWM Convention) which adopts the preventive and/or precautionary approaches. A central problem is that of risk and risk assessment. The law is a key tool to achieve marine ecosystem protection.

The purpose of this Part of the Project is to assist countries to reduce the transfer of harmful organisms in ships' ballast water. This is to be achieved by providing legal assistance, capacity building and institutional strengthening to remove barriers to effective ballast water management arrangements.

This part of the Project will perform several interdependent functions including:

- (a) ***Legislative Review*** – A review and analysis of the legal/administrative environment is essential to ensure effective implementation of governmental policy objectives. It is a key component of the Project. It is necessary first step for any country that intends to implement the BWM Convention. Accordingly, prior to developing a national strategy regarding ballast water issues a country would need to identify relevant international and regional legal obligations and to review its existing national legislation and administrative arrangements. The focus of the Legislative Review is specifically oriented to domestic implementation questions. Nevertheless, a country's international and regional commitments, particularly in trade related sectors, increasingly shape the domestic regulatory regime. They must be considered in order to ensure that legal and institutional infrastructure is integrated and helps to support the country's sustainable development goals. Domestic regulatory efforts to address the problem need to do so in an integrated manner that addresses the full range of issues in order to ensure that the response is effective. In this respect, the Proposal sets out a number of key issues, conclusions and recommendations. Relevant questions will be address, *inter alia*: (a) Do States currently have an international legal obligation to take action to prevent the unintentional transfer of potentially harmful aquatic organisms and pathogens between parts of the marine ecosystem. If so, how is this obligation characterized in international law and does it extend to preventing the transfer in ships' ballast water? (b) Do States have any legal obligations that constrain or otherwise shape their national response to the problem of preventing

ballast water transfer of potentially harmful aquatic organisms and pathogens?

(c) If a State takes regulatory action to deal with the transfer of potentially harmful aquatic organisms and pathogens in ships' ballast water, what principles and goals should inform its strategy? (d) At what level of governance should a State's regulatory response to the problem of transfer of potentially harmful aquatic organisms and pathogens in ships' ballast water be developed? (e) How is the problem of aquatic species and pathogen transfer best characterized in national systems and which agency should be charged with administrative responsibility?

(b) *Effective Regulatory Design in a Time of Change* - Construction and elaboration of legislation to implement effective ballast water management and control measures taking into account key tools, inter alia – (a) General Principles: Precautionary Approach; Ecosystem Approach; State Responsibility; Research and Monitoring; Education and Public Awareness; (b) Prevention: Border Control and Quarantine Measures; Exchange of Information; Cooperation, including Capacity-Building; (b) Introduction of Species: Intentional Introduction; Unintentional Introductions; and (c) Mitigation of Impacts: Mitigation of Impacts; Eradication; Containment; Control. The Project will provide a comprehensive overview of the existing international legal obligations regarding ballast water. Moreover, it will address valuable information on different regulatory approaches around the world and will provide a wide range of basic elements to be addressed in national legislation.

(c) Identification of the Ministries involved - The connection between the human health, biodiversity, economic and other security interests-biosecurity – posed by this issue provides a challenge for existing institutional structures at national and international levels. A number of government Ministries may be implicated, to some degree, in a response to the problem. The intersection of health security, economy, environmental protection and national security concern presents a challenge for coherent governance at the domestic and international levels.

(d) Training Activities - Applied courses for university, students and public administrators; both short and specialized courses aiming professional skills

development; Workshops and Symposiums; Technology transfer for the Atlantic Ocean Control Center.

1.2. Ocean acidity and climate change

Justification

The oceans comprise approximately 71 per cent of the Earth's surface and the total volume of the marine environment provides about 300 times more space for life than that provided by land and freshwater combined. The so-called planet Earth is a vast expanse of blue water.

The marine ecosystem is highly dynamic and interconnected, to the extent that local phenomena can affect activities and processes taking place in distant parts of the globe. Historically, however, attempts to tackle oceanic problems, such as overfishing, were grounded on a piecemeal and sectorialized approach. Thus, marine environmental regulation and governance was drafted domestically and often overlapped or even opposed other municipal policies.

In light of current major challenges for the world's ocean health and the livelihoods dependent on the ocean, it is pressing that national policies and laws be informed by an integrated approach. Sector policies must reflect principles and standards enshrined in national ocean strategies, which in turn ought to reflect international marine environmental normative developments, be them of a binding or non-binding nature.

It is well-known that the increase in water temperatures, added to the acidification of those waters (decrease in pH), will have major impacts on marine life, including fisheries. Ocean acidification may compromise protein supplies from the ocean, thus jeopardizing the principal food source of millions of people that live by the sea. It is so also because reefs, which are responsible for providing habitat and nutrients for fish stocks, are directly impacted by rising temperatures and water acidification. In fact, acidifying oceans have already begun to disrupt local and regional economies that rely on marine resources (IPCC, *Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report*, Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to IPCC AR5, p. 64–73).

Scientists acknowledge that unless the increasing ocean acidification current scenario is reverted, adaptation measures against climate change may stand a chance to succeed. The pH of near surface water should not drop more than a specific quantity (0.2 units) in comparison with pre-industrial levels. The focus for the international community and individual states must, thus, lie on reducing CO²

emissions as “the” alternative for future negotiations under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). The World Meteorological Organization (WMO), its annual Greenhouse Gas Bulletin of 2016, noted that atmospheric carbon dioxide levels reached a record high of 400 parts per million in the previous year. Aware of this worrying figure, it becomes clear that mitigating climate change and its impacts will require building on the momentum achieved by the Paris Agreement on Climate Change, which entered into force on 4 November 2016 (WMO, *Greenhouse Gas Bulletin: the state of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere based on global observations through 2015*, n. 12, 24 October 2016, p. 1).

On the geochemical aspect, consequences of acidification over marine biodiversity are still poorly understood. To tackle such limited knowledge, there has been a surge in researches and publications on this subject, but mainly with a natural sciences stance. Ocean acidity levels are arising due to anthropocentric interference in nature, a phenomenon which is even harder to tackle considering the overlap and antinomies between international and domestic policies and rules fostering the halting of ocean acidification worldwide.

Satellites are the only possible way to both collect and relay data from the ocean. By using many different sensors onboard, satellites collect data about ocean, such as: bathymetry, surface temperature and color, coral reefs, and sea and lake ice. Satellites are also capable of relaying signals from transmitters on the surface such as: tidal heights and the migration of whales. All these data may be fused with many others using specific algorithms in order to provide knowledge and decision-making support. Satellites also dispatch position information from emergency beacons from boats, airplanes, or people in remote areas when in distress.

Proposal

There are just a few international juridical documents that address the ocean acidification, mainly of a non-binding nature. In some national legal systems, the situation may be all the more precarious. For that reason, a collective work on the Law of Ocean Acidification and Climate Change is most timely, so as to inform specialists and decision-makers on policy and legal gaps, as well as to highlight possible legal ways for local communities to tackle local sources of ocean acidification, in order to prevent further nefarious impacts on ecosystems and human societies.

Accordingly, the issue evokes the impact of facts on Law. Hence, it is undeniable that current facts exert a powerful pressure towards the development of adequate legal answers – in this case, the increase in carbon dioxide emissions being absorbed by the oceans, and the resulting decrease in pH of salty water worldwide,

phenomenon known as ocean acidification. Apart from facts, pressure of emerging values and a growing “environmental rationality” is to be felt in the international law-making process.

This Proposal explores the implications of the international legal regime regarding the ocean acidification and climate change on the legal framework and policy with respect to the countries bordering the Triangle Atlantic Ocean. It intends to study how Brazil and Portugal, which are part of the major Conventions on Environmental Law, Law of the Sea and Climate Change and key countries in global ocean governance schemes with bold ambitions seaward, are facing the issue and meeting mitigation and adaptation challenges. Furthermore, the Project will revise the juridical framework on the issue adopted by African countries.

This Part of the Project – on the assessment of ocean acidification and climate change laws and policies in Brazil, Portugal and African countries represents an effort at systematizing existing international law on the issue and its impact on legal realities. The further development of domestic legal orders and shaping of state behavior is ultimately the *raison d’être* for international norms.

To respond to these needs, this proposal will focus on several key issues:

- (a) ***Legislative review*** – Thorough analysis of the dynamics of Brazilian, Portuguese and African recent policy and legislative developments regarding ocean acidification and climate change; the analyzes of the main hindrances to the domestic implementation of international agreements; This Part of the Project explores the implications and evaluation of the national and international legal regime and policy on ocean acidification and climate change on the countries bordering the Atlantic Triangle. The Project will examine existing efforts on the international stage to address the issue of climate change and ocean acidification, in particular resolutions, declarations, and consultative processes, and to what extent they have adequately tackled the issue of ocean acidification. This review poses questions for any country to consider including whether addressing the full range of concerns and responsibilities on ocean acidity requires new or different forms of legal and institutional responses at the national level or not.
- (b) ***Overview with respect to the international legal framework on ocean acidification and climate change – from soft law to hard law*** - The impact of *soft law* on the development and codification of the law of the sea and climate change law is unquestionable, as several binding instruments in those regimes flow down, *inter alia*, from *soft law* instruments; to examine existing efforts on the international

stage to address the issue of climate change and ocean acidification, in particular resolutions, declarations, and consultative processes, and to what extent they have adequately tackled the issue of ocean acidification. The plethora of *soft law* on ocean acidification and climate change indicates towards the viability of and international desire to an international binding regulation prescribing objectives and mechanisms to avoid widespread water acidification.

- (c) ***The impact of international law regarding the issue on the Brazilian, Portuguese and African domestic order*** - International binding norms on climate change and ocean acidity are scarce. A major reference is the 1992 UNFCCC, aimed at tackling atmospheric pollution by carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases so as to prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with climate dynamics. The treaty's objectives are known to include achieving sustainable management of reservoirs of greenhouse gases, which include oceans. Ocean acidification has been an important topic for the UNFCCC's Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA) research dialogue. As an effort to implement the UNFCCC, several parties signed the Paris Agreement in 2015, adopted at the Conference of the Parties (COP) 21. In that binding instrument, states have agreed to work towards the ambitious goal to limit temperature rise below 2 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels, and to strive for 1.5 degrees. There one single mention to "oceans" in the Agreement, in its Preamble, when parties note the importance of insuring the integrity of all ecosystems, oceans included, before taking action against climate change. Despite the absence of references to "acidification" in the Agreement, parties have agreed on the need to implement several mitigation and mitigation measures, which would lead to less carbon dioxide in the atmosphere, less absorption of greenhouse gases by the oceans and reduced water acidification. Those long-term objectives and global mitigation measures are certainly a starter. However, there are other local measures that communities can take to minimize stressors to ocean health, such as regulating land-based pollution, irresponsible tourism and overfishing. It is relevant to assess the extent of which such activities impact on ocean acidification and whether new laws and policies are needed to tackle traditional stressors as the ones mentioned supra. Another relevant, albeit limited instrument, is the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), which imposes on parties the

obligation to prevent pollution of the oceans from any sources, including the atmosphere. Besides, the Convention includes a definition of marine “pollution”, which encompasses the indirect introduction of anthropogenic carbon dioxide into the marine environment, a main driver of ocean acidification. Apart from the aforementioned binding instruments, the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) also indirectly deals with the issue of ocean acidification, inasmuch as the phenomenon interferes with the implementation of all three objectives of the Convention: conservation of biological diversity, sustainable use of biological components, equitable sharing of benefits from the utilization of genetic resources. Hence, any measure to promote conservation of marine biodiversity must take ocean acidification and mitigation of CO² emissions into account.

- (d) ***The implementing structure, monitoring and evaluation of national policies, institutions and rules designed to minimize ocean acidity levels;***
- (e) ***A long-term outlook onto the issue*** - which may offer ways to enhance national legislation and policy on ocean acidity and climate change regarding this much unexplored and understudied topic;
- (f) ***Review and analysis of the legal/administrative environment.***- Although technical matters, science, ecological and commercial issues are fundamental and affect every regulatory design on ocean acidification and climate changes, they were not described in detail in this proposal, which focused specifically on the legal implications of these issues. Improvement of national legislation and policies; tackling local sources of ocean acidification and cooperation with neighboring states are key issues required to avoid the increase of marine pollution. The role of law and policy in achieving healthier and more productive marine ecosystems is pivotal;

2. Fisheries

Justification

The Operational Program (OP) for the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) in Portugal for 2014-2020 aims at achieving key national development

priorities along with the EU's "Europe 2020" objectives. The OP's main objectives include enhancing the competitiveness and viability of the fisheries and aquaculture business in Portugal, strengthening technological development, innovation and transfer of knowledge to fishery and aquaculture business, and improving the common markets organization.

The issue of fisheries, which, if not well preserved, could be easily exploited and devastated, similarly to what happened in Somalia in the recent past. This is a concern, particularly considering that some of Atlantic coastline countries still face major economic challenges, which could generate domestic and regional instability. These issues need to be addressed quickly.

The lack of natural resources strengthens structures that set incentives for exploiting comparative cost advantages and enable a process of wealth creation, supported by what has been termed a developmental State. The presence of resource wealth evokes distributional conflicts around the capture of resource rents, which distort the relationship between ruling elites, the state and society. These phenomena economic and social structures, they discourage other productive activities.

Good institutions are thought to intercept an otherwise negative relationship by ensuring that resource policies and resource revenue management are conducted to serve the public rather than particular private interests. This principle is evidently applied to combating illegal fishing and monitoring the origin and route of legal fishing.

Satellites are a suitable tool for combatting illegal fishing and follow the origin and route of legal fishing. Using numerous sources including satellite positioning, imagery, and vessel identification, data are gathered and analyzed by using advanced computer algorithms to acquire knowledge and have accurate, trustworthy picture of the activities on the oceans. Data integration and situational awareness make it possible business and governments to deliver solutions. These new services are addressing the challenges of illegal fishing, monitoring Marine Protected Areas and Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ) and supporting supply chain transparency.

Proposal

This part of the Project addresses tools to promote a sustainable fishery based on specific legal framework aiming the protection of the marine ecosystem biodiversity, evoking the elaboration of rules to promote a competitive fishery based on environmental principles, *inter alia*, the preventive and precautionary approach; no harm principle; international cooperation; transfer of technology and the polluter pay.

The Proposal encompasses several essential legal matters, including

- a. The impact of national law/international law on the issue and the challenges;
- b. The impact of the legal regime of fishery in the Economic Exclusive Zone (EEZ) and the protection of the marine environment;
- c. Revision of the Sovereignty rights concept;
- d. Revision of the rules addressed in UNCLOS;
- e. Orientation with respect to the adoption of adequate legal framework to the protection of the marine environment and fishery;
- f. Holistic approach *vis-à-vis* the teleology of the legal framework addressed, *inter alia*, by the Ministry of Fishery, Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Defense and Ministry of Science and Technology;
- g. Legal adviser under the teleology adopted by ITLOS and ICJ.

3. Law of the Sea and Space Law: Interaction Aiming to Protect the Oceans

Justification

If we are to protect, preserve, and conserve the oceans for our life and health and for the benefit of future generations, we must use the view from space and look as closely as possible at the dynamic forces that stir the colors of the ocean. The oceans are a key element for the existence of life on Earth. The atmosphere we breathe, and which controls the weather and climate, is intimately connected to the oceans. This water mass is an enormous space with a colossal influence to mankind. Certainly, it is crucial to keep a constant surveillance on its health and changes. Temperature, currents, salinity, and pollution are some examples of features that have direct effects on human daily life and the only possible way to keep constant measurements on these and others parameters is using satellites for remote sensing.

Sea and outer space feature strong interactions as media, although they are obviously different. As stars were in the past, satellites are the modern day main tool for navigation and, in this case, there are dozens of platforms around the Earth sending reference signals for ships to keep their tracks. Vessels identification and tracking make use of the Automatic Identification System (AIS). Voice calls are also possible using services such as Inmarsat.

Furthermore, satellites are platforms conceived to provide a variety of services and are mandatory in the management of both normal and disaster situations (either in the sea or due to natural events, such as floods, in isolate locations or when basic infrastructure is destroyed). Some or all services may be necessary: remote sensing, telecommunications, navigation support, asset identification, and positioning. Aircrafts are also useful in complement to satellites.

Another matter to be verified carefully is related to issues posed by unmanned aircraft and satellites to sovereignty. What regime will be applied to the Unmanned Aerial Vehicles on the oceans? How to define operational mechanisms for triggering a chain of command in a given country or region of the world due to an information obtained from a satellite? What happens if the data sent by navigation satellites are wrong and cause an accident or financial loss?

Proposal

From a holistic perspective, this part of Project intends to provide essential tools and information regarding the interconnection space technology/ space law *vis-a-vis* the legal protection of the oceans and to construct the impact of the law of the sea on the development of a space law teleology toward a sustainable Earth. Accordingly, this Part of the Project encompasses:

- a. Practical Aspects with respect to the utilization of space technology to achieve information on the *state of art* regarding the marine environment and safety and security of the oceans;
- b. Theoretical knowledge regarding the impact of the law of the sea international legal framework on the structure and teleology of space law: revision of the Sovereignty concept; Sovereign rights; freedom of high seas; freedom of navigation; freedom of scientific investigation; freedom of exploitation; the common heritage of mankind; innocent passage; jurisdiction of the State of registry; international cooperation and transfer of technology;
- c. Practical orientation and construction related to the complex coexistence between the law of the sea and space law with respect to coastal State sovereignty and Sovereign rights. The IOC/UNESCO ARGO Program is an example regarding the legal framework overlap of the sea/space law regimes applied to floats deployed on the world oceans and monitored via remote sensing.

Accordingly, this part of the Project reviews the legal paradigms adopted by space law *vis-a-vis* the development of space technology and the interface with oceans issue, particularly the Sovereignty and the impact of Unilateral Acts on the development of the law of the sea and space law, i.e., revisiting the traditional sources of international law.

Appendix C - Good Order at Sea: Maritime Safety and Security Challenges

Justification

Steinberg has already highlighted that as humankind take account of the role of the ocean as a valuable source of economic resources. For some States, it represents the only opportunity of future development. Nevertheless, the ocean has been submitted to a social constructive process that shapes its traditional political, social, and economic conditions: from a merely space to be used by society - a merely space to serve land-based societies - to become one component of the proper space of society. Because of this social construction many international relations initiatives and programs are increasingly devoting attention to maritime spaces – both their strategic value and their political-cultural and socio-economic connections.

Ocean basins are not considered any more as vast surfaces separating people, or merely as transit routes for various flows of goods or people. They are now considered as platforms for the potential convergence of littoral regions around shared political and socio-economic agendas. They have become sources of structural power. They have become connectors among people and nations, instead of barriers to be surmounted.

Accordingly, oceans require regulation and rules and "governance of the oceans" grows in importance among the concerns of the international community. The United Nations Convention on Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) is the regime *par excellence* for ordering the shared use of the seas and their resources. Nevertheless, concerns about oceans have never been so high, and Nations have been developing maritime procedures and strategies in order to better harmonize their political and economic established interests, resources, and goals in order the good order at sea to be assured.

Good order at sea means: preserving marine habitats; fighting pirates and sea robbers; countering drug trafficking, illicit trade of light weapons, and illegal traffic of people; combating illegal, unregulated and unreported (IUU) fishing; and dealing with climate change problems; in sum, to tackle what have been known as “new threats.” “New threats”, notwithstanding some conceptual divergence, present a unanimous approach – they have, with no exception, transnational character. Consequently, it is mandatory that the Nations cooperate in order to counter act transnationally.

Nations have to improve efforts towards fostering international institutional ties and agreements, aiming to share knowledge, best practices, and experiences at different levels. Above all, they need to contribute to the construction of instruments of governance for the oceans able to meet the existing threats and challenges.

Good order at the sea is both a subject of growing geopolitical salience and a field of expanding regional cooperation. This is due to the need to counter illicit flows, the discoveries of large off-shore energy reserves, the increasing volumes of maritime trade and the challenge of piracy. Piracy mainly targets the oil and gas industry and takes a heavy toll on the economies of affected countries.

In the Atlantic, energy landscape is facing considerable change. The area accounts for about 60% of offshore oil discoveries in the last 20 years and for an equivalent amount of global offshore oil production – a share that jumps to 95% when considering ‘deep’ offshore only (much of that localized in the Southern Atlantic).

The Atlantic is a region of deep interdependence and broadly shared challenges. However, still features fragmented cooperation and loose political convergence. Partnerships have to be increased among countries in the region to consolidate a cooperative framework. As Ambassador Florentina Ukonga addressed in a Maritime Security Conference at Chatam House, in 2012: “National, bilateral and international actions in tackling issues of maritime security in the Gulf of Guinea will be more effective if they fit into a region-wide strategy for maritime security.”

The potential for cooperation within the Atlantic is vast. However, different historical experiences and normative reflexes continue to hinder joint approaches. Aside from a variety of regional and inter-regional dialogue and cooperation institutions and initiatives, it is still difficult to discern a pattern of political convergence between the sub-regions of the Atlantic, thus, trust is one important condition to unlock this potential.

Overlapping regional institutions may present a good opportunity for confidence building measures to get a cooperative environment able to carry out transnational efforts to face threats that cannot be met by an isolate Nation. Atlantic contains several of these regional institutions: South Atlantic Peace and Cooperation Zone (ZPACAS or ZOPACAS), Gulf of Guinea Commission (GoGC) and Community of Portuguese Language Countries (CPLP).

ZPACAS was create in 1986 through resolution A/Res/41/11 of the UN General Assembly, on Brazil’s initiative, aiming to promote cooperation and the maintenance of peace and security in the South Atlantic. Presently, it consists of 24 countries, including Argentina, Brazil, and Uruguay from the South American side, and all countries on the West African coast, except for Morocco and Mauritania. Having been conceived in the Cold War context, this organization could have taken advantage of the shift in threat perception after the fall of the Berlin Wall to refocus on unconventional threats, particularly transnational organized crime and terrorism. This new emphasis was not a novelty though. ZPACAS main objectives since its creation were: To defend independence, sovereignty, territorial integrity and develop relations under conditions of peace and freedom; To protect the region from militarization, the arms race, the presence of foreign military bases and, above all,

nuclear weapons; To stimulate regional cooperation for economic development and peace; To encourage international peace and security by eliminating all sources of tension in the region and encouraging the protection of the environment and the conservation of the resources of the vast oceanic area.

For combatting transnational crime and illicit to assure good order at the Atlantic, it is necessary to improve cheaper and useful activities available for cooperation against transnational organized crime, such as information exchange, crime analysis, drug profiling, or criminal justice. To accomplish this, it is wise to use the existing structure of ZPACAS broadening its competences so that it can handle both political-military affairs and transnational organized crime issues.

A Declaration on the denuclearization of the South Atlantic region was adopted in Brazilian in September 1994. Currently, the South Atlantic is a nuclear-weapon-free zone. All member states are signatories of international treaties that prohibit nuclear weapons, namely the African Nuclear Free Zone Treaty for Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons in Latin America and the Caribbean.

The relationship between peace preservation in the South Atlantic and the maintenance of this region as a Nuclear or mass destruction Weapon-Free Zone and the resulting benefits to security and prosperity for Latin America, the Caribbean, Africa and Antarctica is an essential issue.

In what concerns the GoGC, it was born out of the treaty signed in Libreville, Gabon, on 3 July 2001 by Angola, Congo, Gabon, Nigeria and Sao Tome and Principe. The GoGC is a permanent institutional tool for the cooperation of these States bordering the Gulf of Guinea, with a view to defending their common interests and promoting peace and socio-economic development based on dialogue and concerted actions, based on the bonds of friendship, solidarity and fraternity that unite them. Cameroon and the Democratic Republic of Congo joined the Commission in 2008, and it remains open to the accession of other States on the coast of the Gulf of Guinea, with a view to transforming the sub region, which has emerged as a global hydrocarbon-producing power, into a peace and security zone.

It is relevant to emphasize that ZPACAS geographically encompasses the GoGC region. Besides, as both institutions have quite similar objectives, to implement confidence measures building seems easier than in other maritime regions.

The CPLP is essentially a community in which the sea, as an identity vector, has an undeniable, multidimensional and multidisciplinary importance and is therefore a unique identity vector that allows its States to unite with the structuring factors of the common language and history, as well as its management, preservation and sustainability. Seven of the nine CPLP member States are in the Atlantic rim land. Because of that, Atlantic is considered the main maritime area of CPLP, particularly the Gulf of Guinea region with all its circumstances like piracy, trafficking in persons and narcotics, illegal migratory flows, arms trafficking and energy resources. Being

connected to ZPACAS and GoGC by common participants, CPLP attracts Portugal to their maritime areas. This addition gives the Community an added geopolitical value and to Portugal a privileged geostrategic position within the Atlantic.

Piracy

The issue relates to safe trading and the increase of Piracy, in particular at the Atlantic West coast of Africa¹, see Fig. 1. The problems with piracy increased in 2018, only in the first semester were registered 107 attacks against 87 in all the year 2017. Regarding these issues, the Project may explore possible measures to mitigate the causes which are threatening maritime transports lines. It proposes, for instance, joint security arrangements between countries and support authorities for decision-making, via the use of cutting edge technologies (data gathering, connectivity, storage, access, and analysis). Current technologies allow for a paradigm shift in the fight against piracy: a digital transformation.

Fig. 1. Total piracy incidents between January and June of 2018. Source: Mariama Sow, Figures of the week: *Piracy increasing in the Gulf of Guinea*. August 2, 2018.

Proposal

This project proposes a feasibility study for the creation of an information center (data analyses system) focusing on piracy issues. The feasibility study shall consider a system with information generated through the analysis of diverse data with

¹ Mariama Sow, Figures of the week: Piracy increasing in the Gulf of Guinea. August 2, 2018.

specialized algorithms of artificial intelligence (satellite and aeronautical imagery, social, and meteorological, for example) to provide a clear situation examination and support to the decision making in the light of the country's political-legal system. The project aims to determine potential positives and negatives outcomes of an information center for support governments decision-making.

Accordingly, this Part of the Project encompasses:

- a. Focus on the following countries: Brazil, Guinea-Bissau, Sao Tome and Principe, and Democratic Republic of Congo.
- b. Analysis of the political-legal system of the countries of interest.
- c. Initial analyses of an information center at the countries of interest:
 - i. Data storage structure and Big Data processing, focusing on piracy, using various data analysis through specialized algorithms of artificial intelligence;
 - ii. Use of satellite and aeronautical data fused to diverse data;
 - iii. Creation of an interconnect network of Regional Information Centers;
 - iv. Constraints due to each country's political-legal structure.

Appendix D: Curricula Vitarum

Artur Victoria

Full Name: Artur Alexandre Feio de Victoria Candeias

Portuguese nationality

BI Number or Citizen Card: 2726726

Profession: Lawyer

Position: Consultant

E-mail: arturvictoria@gmail.com

Phone: **inserir ddd e código de área** 933304213

Academic qualifications:

- degree in Law at the University of Lisbon - 1974 and,
- National Defence Course in 1989.
- European Training Course for Teachers and Trainers.

Current Academic positions held:

- Researcher on migration and security at CEPESE - University of Porto
- Senior Researcher at OBSERVARE - Peace and War Program in the New International Relations - Autonomous University of Lisbon Luís de Camões

Honorary Mentions and Decorations:

- Friend of the **Brazilian** Navy;
- Adesguian Merit Medal **Brazilian or Portuguese?**;
- Marechal Mascarenhas de Morais Medal **Brazilian or Portuguese**;
- Honorary member of the Brazilian Air Force;
- **Emérito inserir em inglês** of the Brazilian Army
- Medal of Merit of the Portuguese Army D. Afonso Henriques - silver rank
- Order of Aeronautical Merit, **Brazilian or Portuguese**
- **Brazilian Navy** Tamandaré Merit Medal

Currently Activities:

- Delegate in Europe of the Federation of Chambers of Commerce and Industry of South America;
- President of SOAMAR Brasil in Portugal, coordinating delegates to the CPLP and Europe;
- President of the Delegation in Portugal of the Association of Diplomates of the Superior School of War - Brazil;
- President of the Association of Friends of the Armed Forces;
- Promotes and supports, annually, at the University of Minho a course on armed conflicts;
- Conducts semiannual debates on Geopolitics in the section "Brazil and the South Atlantic";
- Works with the Army, Navy and Air Force of Brazil, especially through its Social Communication Centers to publicize the main projects of the Brazilian Armed Forces, in progress, lectures in Portugal and in Europe with the objective of disseminating the Doctrine of the School Superior of War - ESG;
- It is developing a project driven by the Adity of the Army and Aeronautics of Brazil for the installation of the "Luso-Brazilian Pedagogical Museum" in partnership with the Air Force and Army of Brazil and Portugal.
- The PROSUB - the Navy's program in the CPLP and in Europe
- It is an element of civil-military contact with the Strategic Analysis Centre (CAE / CPLP), based in Maputo.

Maria Helena Fonseca de Souza Rolim

Brazilian nationality

ID: 4.422808

Profession: Lawyer

Position: Consultant

E-mail: mhrolim@terra.com.br

Phone: + + 55 11 5052 9308
983055665

Academic qualifications:

- Bachelor's Degree in Law (LLB), Faculty of Law University of São Paulo, 1972.
- Master's Degree in International Law/Maritime Law (MLB), Faculty of Law, University of São Paulo, 1975.
- Specialist in Environmental Law, United States of America, Fulbright Commission, Texas International Education Consortium, LBJ School of Public Affairs, The University of Texas of Austin, 1988.
- Doctorate in International Law/Law of the Sea comparative Japanese Law (Ph.D), Faculty of Law, University of São Paulo, 1993.
- Visiting Scholar, Space Law, Space Policy Institute of George Washington University's Elliot School of International Affairs, 2001.
- Researcher, Chinese Space Law and Policy, Harbin Institute of Technology, China, 1996/1997.

Professional Activities

- Legal Adviser, Brazilian Government and foreign Governments, since 1975.
- Legal Consultant, Federation of Industries of the State of São Paulo, 1990/2000.
- Legal Adviser, Space Law and Law of the Sea, United Nations Organization (FAO, IMO, IOC/UNESCO), since 1990.
- Legal Adviser, Brazilian National Institute of Space Research, Space Law, 1993/2001.
- Brazilian Local Legal Adviser, GLOBALLAST PROGRAMME, UN/IMO/World Maritime University, Sweden, 2002.
- Director, Fonseca de Souza Rolim & Suannes Law Firm, Brazil, 1990/2013.
- Participation as lecturer, researcher and/or legal adviser in Argentina, Australia, Austria (UN/COPUOS), Brazil (National Institute for Space Research), Chile (Permanent Commission for the South Pacific), China (Harbin Institute of High Technology), Colombia (ROCRAN), France (IOC/UNESCO/UN; IAF), Germany(University of Cologne; German Space Agency) , Italy (FAO), Malta (IMO/UN/International Maritime Law Institute), Mozambique (FAO; World Bank), Norway (Scandinavian Institute of Maritime Law/Oslo University), Portugal (Portuguese Trade Association), Singapore (National University of Singapore/Korea Institute of Ocean Science & Technology/ Berkeley Law – Law of the Sea Institute/Centre for International Law);Slovenia (Faculty of Maritime Studies and Transportation, University of Ljubljana; Sweden (UN/World Maritime University), United Kingdom (IMO/UN) and United States of America (Space Policy Institute; NASA).

Didactic Activities

- Doctorate Professor, International Law, Faculty of Law, University of São Paulo, São Paulo 1989/1996.
- Visiting Professor, International Financial Law, Course of Banking Law, Bank of Mozambique, Mozambique, United Nations Organization, World Bank, 1994/1995.
- General Coordinator, Post Graduation Course on Space Law and Outer Space International Management, UNIVAP/ INPE/ AEB/ NASA/ SBDA, São José dos Campos, Brazil, 1999.

- Professor, Post- Graduation Course, Space Law, Instituto Tecnológico de Aeronáutica (ITA), São José dos Campos, Brazil, 2002/2003.
- Associate Professor, Law of the Sea, Scandinavian Institute of Maritime Law, Oslo University, Norway, 2004/2006.
- Professor, Space Law, Faculty of Space Engineering, Brazilian Air Force, Technological Institute of Aeronautics (ITA), 2012.
- Visiting Professor, UN/IMO International Maritime Law Institute, Malta, since 2014.
- Visiting Lecturer, Law of the Sea, Scandinavian Institute of Maritime Law, Oslo University, Norway, 2016.
- Guest Lecturer, UN/World Maritime University, Sweden, 2018.

Publications

- Publications with respect to International Law, Law of the Sea and Space Law in Brazil, Chile, France, Germany, Japan, Mozambique, The Netherlands , Portugal and United Kingdom.

Publications, inter alia

The Impact of the Law of the Sea on the Development of Space Law: From Lege Ferenda to Lege Lata: An Odyssey to the Unknown in Prospects of Evolution of the Environmental Law and the Practice of ITLOS: New Challenges and Emerging Regimes, Ndiaye *et all* editors, Brasil, 2018; *The International Law on Ballast Water: Preventing Biopollution*, Martinus Nijhoff, The Netherlands, 2008; *Brazilian Investor's Guide, FIESP, Germany, 1997*; *Buraziru Kaihatsu hoo no shosoo : Mercosuuru to shin Kokusai Tchitsujo*, Asia Keisei Kenkyusha, Japan, 1994; *Banking Law: Mozambique Bank*, Mozambique Bank, 1994; *Juridical Aspects of Brazil/ Portugal Commercial Relations*, Journal of Foreign Trade, Portugal, 1988.

Information Regarding Activities Outside Brazil

- Malta-Msida: International Maritime Law Institute/ International Maritime Organization, invited professor since 2014.
- France-Paris: Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission/UNESCO, 2009, Legal Adviser regarding the juridical framework of the “Argo Programme”.
- Norway-Oslo: Scandinavian Institute of Maritime Law, Oslo University, 2004-2006, Associate Professor.
- England-London: The Global Environment Facility (GEF) / the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)/ International Maritime Organization (IMO)/Brazilian Ministry of Environment (MMA): **GLOBALLAST PROGRAMME**, Brazilian **GLOBALLAST PROGRAMME**, 2001-2002, Brazilian Local Legal Adviser.
- United States of America- Washington: NASA: 1993 – 2000, Legal Adviser to the Brazilian Ministry of Science and Technology regarding the Brazilian International Space Station Program *in tandem* with NASA.
- China – Harbin/Beijing: 1996-1997, Legal Adviser with respect to the CBRSS Program. Researcher with respect to Space Law at Peking University and Harbin University.
- Italy-Rome/Mozambique-Maputo: Food and Agriculture Organizations of the United Nations: 1990-1991, Expert on Mission, FAO legal adviser

Other Activities

- Member of the Political-Strategic Studies Center, Brazilian Navy, since 2017;
- Member of the Brazilian Navy Society Friend, since 1993;
- Member of the Superior Council of Foreign Trade, Federation of Industries of the State of São Paulo (FIESP), since 2015;
- *Rapporteur* of the Brazilian Senate Commission on the Brazilian Air Code Revision, 2015 -2016;

- Member of the International Institute of Space Law of the International Astronautical Federation, since 1999;
- Member of the Brazilian Society of Air – Space Law, since 1995.

Honors (Awards)

Honorary Professor of International Law, Faculty of Law, “Vale do Paraíba University”, São Paulo, Brazil, 2000;

Navy Medal, Brazilian Navy Ministry, 1993;

Honorary Professor of International Law/Maritime Law/Law of the Sea, Municipal Institute for Higher Research, MBA, São Paulo, Brazil, 1984.

ANDRE LUIZ PIERRE MATTEI

Nacionalities: French and Brazilian

Currently director of an applied research center, Senai Institute of Innovation for Embedded Systems, and Colonel (Ret.) with over a thousand flight hours in military aircraft. Member of both the Committee of the Defense Industries of the State of Santa Catarina and the Chamber of Technology and Innovation of the Industry Federation of the State of Santa Catarina. Industrial applied research focusing on IIoT, Industry 4.0, Autonomous machines, and Aerospace (satellite and UAV systems).

EXPERIENCE

After 07/2016	Chief Science Officer Senai Innovation Institute for Embedded Systems. The Institute conducts applied research in industries for advanced manufacturing, IoT, aerospace systems, and system control.
09/2015 - 07/2016	Visiting Professor - ISAE-Supaéro, Toulouse, France Research in the field of Microsatellites and UAVs.
02/1984 - 08/2015	Military Officer of the Brazilian Air Force Retired as Colonel.
04/2010 - 08/2015	Professor at Instituto Tecnológico de Aeronáutica, ITA, Brazil Research in the field of Microsatellites and UAVs.
04/2013 - 01/2014	Visiting Professor – Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), Cambridge, US Cooperation ITA-MIT; Research in the field of Microsatellites and UAVs.
05/2012 - 08/2015	Representative of Science and Technology Department of the Brazilian Air Force Design of the Space Systems Strategic Plan for the Ministry of Defense.
05/2010 - 04/2013	Coordinator of the under graduation course in Aerospace at ITA ITA is an engineering university with focus in aerospace.
03/2009 - 04/2010	Managing Director of Elimco-Brasil Responsible for Elimco installation in Brazil and support for the subsidiaries in Colombia and Chile. Elimco is a Spanish company.
04/2008 - 03/2009	Business Development - Sygma Group Contracts in Brazil, US, and Colombia. Sygma Group is a Brazilian consulting company.
10/2007 - 04/2008	Head of Engineering - Sygma Group Responsible for a stationary gas turbine development.
12/1999 - 10/2007	Technical Manager P-3BR (maritime patrol aircraft) e C-295 (light transport aircraft)
02/1997 - 12/2004	Scientific Researcher Fiber optic sensors and Electronic Warfare systems.
12/1987 - 12/1991	Military Pilot Maritime Patrol and Attack, Brazilian Air Force.

EDUCATION

2018-2019	Postdoctoral Fellow in Computer Science Institute of Mathematics and Computer Sciences, USP, Brazil.
2012-2015	PhD in Computer Science Institute of Mathematics and Computer Sciences, USP, Brazil.
2002-2004	MBA in Business Strategy Superior School of Advertising and Marketing, ESPM, Brazil.
1997-1998	Master in Physics Aeronautics Institute of Technology, ITA, Brazil.
1992-1996	Bachelor in Electronic Engineering Aeronautics Institute of Technology, ITA, Brazil.
1984-1987	Military Officer and Pilot Air Force Academy, AFA, Brazil.

LANGUAGES

Portuguese, English, French, and Spanish.

CURRICULUM VITAE

VICTOR ALENCAR MAYER FEITOSA VENTURA

Bieberstr. 1, Zi. 510, 20146, Hamburg

Tel.: (49) 0157 36646869

Email: vfventura@gmail.com

e-CV: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/7804619127088289>

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Date of Birth	January 05 th 1988
Place of Birth	Sousa – Brazil
Marital Status	Single
Citizenship	Brazilian
Passport Number	FK927247

FORMAL EDUCATION

Jan. 2015 –	University of Hamburg (UHH), Germany PhD Candidate in International Law Dissertation: <i>The Environmental Dimension of the “Brazilian Blue Amazon” Concept: exploitation on Outer Continental Shelves between sovereignty rights and environmental obligations in the Law of the Sea.</i> First Supervisor: Prof. Dr. iur. Stefan Oeter Second Supervisor: Prof. Dr. iur Henning Jessen
Mar. 2017	International Seabed Authority (ISA) and German Environment Agency (UBA), Berlin, Germany Workshop on the Environmental Management Strategy for the Area – Law of the Sea Coordinators: Dr. Michael Lodge and Dr. Harald Ginzky
Jul. 2015 – Aug. 2015	International Foundation for the Law of the Sea (IFLOS), Hamburg, Germany Summer Academy on “Promoting Ocean Governance and Peaceful Settlement of Disputes” Winner of Moot Court Competition Coordinator: Prof. Dr. Doris König
Jun. 2015	University of the Faroe Islands, Torshavn, FO Summer Academy on the Continental Shelf and the Law of the Sea (SACS) Coordination: Prof. Dr. Bjorn Kunoy
May 2015	Max Planck Institute for Comparative Public Law and International Law, Heidelberg, Germany 4 th Max Planck Masterclass in International Law “Global Justice and the purpose of International Law” Professor Dr. Emmanuelle Tourme-Jouannet Coordination: Profs. Drs. Armin von Bogdandy and Anne Peters

- Feb. 2011 – Mar. 2013 **Federal University of Paraiba (UFPB), Brazil**
 Master of Laws (LL.M.) in International Human Rights Law
 Dissertation: *The Greening of International Humanitarian Law: perspectives for improved environmental protection during armed conflicts.*
 Supervisor: Prof. Dr. iur. Sven Peterke
- Jan. 2013 – Feb. 2013 **University of Leipzig, Germany**
 Winter Course on German Language, C1, DAAD-Fellow
 Coordinator: Prof. Dr. Maren Eike
- Sep. 2009 – Apr. 2010 **University of Hamburg, Germany**
 Exchange Student, Law Faculty of the University of Hamburg
 Coordinator: Prof. Dr. iur. Robert Freitag
- Mar. 2009 – Jun. 2009 **Superior School Foundation of the Public Ministry of Paraiba, Brazil**
 Specialization Course on Civil Procedural Law
 Professor Dr. Martsung Alencar
- Feb. 2006 – Dec. 2010 **Federal University of Paraiba, Brazil**
 Bachelor of Laws
 Thesis: *The Protection of the Environment by Human Rights: limitations and possibilities.*
 Supervisor: Prof. Dr. iur. Sven Peterke
- Sep. 2005 – Dec. 2005 **University of Coimbra, Portugal**
 Graduation of Laws (1 Trimester)
- Sep. 2002 – Aug. 2005 **High School Infanta Dona Maria Coimbra, Portugal**
 Final Mark: 16,1 values (out of 20)

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

- Sep. 2017 **Brazilian Embassy to Germany**
 Consular Division of the Brazilian Embassy in Hamburg
Pro Bono Consultancy to the Brazilian Community
- Jan. 2017 **University of Hamburg, Germany**
 Lecturer of Foreign Legal Language (*Fremdsprache Seminar*)
 Course: Practical Aspects of the Law of the Sea: current challenges and future perspectives
 28 hours/Semester
- Feb. 2016 **International Conference on Maritime Security and the Law of the Sea, Berlin, Germany**
Special Rapporteur appointed by the German-Japanese Center Berlin (JDZB)
- Jul. 2015 – Sep. 2015 **International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS), Hamburg, Germany**
 Intern of the Legal Office
 Research paper: "The legal environmental status of the Outer Continental Shelf in the Law of the Sea"

	Supervisor: Dr. Yara Saab (Legal Officer)
Jul.2014 – Dec.2014	Integrated Faculties of Patos, Patos, Brazil Professor of Administrative and Commercial Law 120 hours/Semester
Sep. 2011 – Dec. 2012	Carlos Chagas Foundation, São Paulo, Brazil Fellow Researcher Project: “The strengthening of Human Rights’ Lecturing and Researching in the Southern Hemisphere” Coordinator: Prof. Dr. Sandra Unbehaum
Mar. 2011 – Jul. 2011	Federal University of Paraiba, Brazil Faculty of Human Sciences Supervisor in the course on Introduction to Law Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Gustavo Rabay
Apr. 2010 – Dec. 2010	State Court of Paraiba, Brazil Intern at the 6 th Court of the Public Treasury Supervisor: Judge Carlos Sarmiento
Aug. 2008 – Aug. 2009	Federal University of Paraiba, Brazil Researcher and fellow of the National Council for Scientific Research (CNPq) in the project “The implementation of the democratic budget in Joao Pessoa: a case study” Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Fredys Sorto
May 2007 – May 2008	Union of Law Students, UFPB, Brazil Coordinator of Communication and Culture
Sep. 2007	Federal University of Paraiba, Brazil Member of the Organizing Commission of the VII International Human Rights Conference of the Centre for Juridical Sciences of UFPB.
Jul. 2006 – Jul. 2007	Federal University of Paraiba, Brazil Supervisor in the course on Political Science Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Ana Adelaide Guedes Pereira Rosa

RESEARCH PROJECTS

May 2013 –	University of Brasília, Brazil Member of Research Group on “Critique and International Law” Correspondent in Germany Coordinator: Prof. Dr. George Bandeira Galindo
Aug. 2011 – Dec. 2012	Federal University of Paraiba, Brazil Member of Research Group on Rhetoric and Law Coordinator: Prof. Dr. Narbal de Marsillac
2007 – 2008	Federal University of Paraiba, Brazil Member of Human Rights’ Field Work Group “Flor de Mandacaru” Coordinator: Prof. Dr. Maria Luiza Feitosa

Ambassador Rubens Antonio Barbosa

Master the "London School of Economics and Political Science" (School of Economics and Policies of London) in 1971,

Chief negotiator for Brazil in the Uruguay Round GATT then until 1999; President of the Association of Coffee Producing Countries (APPC) in London for five years.; Ambassador of Brazil to the Latin American Integration Association (ALADI) (1987-1990);; Brazil's ambassador in London from January 1994 to June 1999 ; Ambassador in Washington from June 1999 to March 2004.

Ambassador Barbosa writes regularly in the newspaper O Estado de São Paulo and is the author of essays and four books, among which are: Mercosul and Regional Integration, The Dissent Washington (2011) and the National Interest and Future Vision (2012).

Business consultant with extensive network of expertise in the public and private sector

President of the Superior Council of Foreign Trade of FIESP the last ten years; Chairman of the Board of SOBEET (Brazilian Society of Transnational Corporations and Economic Globalization); President Emeritus of Brazil-US Business Council; President of the Institute of International Relations and Foreign Trade (IRICE); Editor of the journal National Interest.; President of the Brazilian Association of Wheat Industry (ABITRIGO); Member of several other councils, as the company's CSU CardSystem SA and Veirano Lawyers; Member of the Board - Business Sao Paulo;

Member of the Council of International Relations of the Government of Sao Paulo.

MARCUS V. FREITAS

Avenida Angélica, 1280

Apt. #52

São Paulo, SP 01228-100

Brazil

Mobile: +55 (11) 9-7641-1833

freitasmv@aol.com

www.marcusvfreitas.com.br

PERSONAL ASSETS

- **Multicultural**, fluent in 4 languages (Portuguese, English, Spanish and French), having visited more than 60 countries for work
- **Capable to engage, motivate and develop people for performance improvement**, in small or large organization, through planning and usage of all the necessary resources to achieve effective results
- **Wide professional experience in Brazil and abroad**, in the public and private sectors, having spent almost 10 years abroad
- **A widely recognized analyst for economic and political scenarios**, at the national and international levels

Education

- M.A., International Relations, Johns Hopkins University – Washington, DC 1996-1999
- LL.M., International Law, Cornell University – Ithaca, NY 1995-1995
- LL.B., Law, University of Sao Paulo – Sao Paulo, SP 1986-1992
- Harold Gordon Hiram Fellowship for graduate studies in Law
- Organization of American States (OAS) Fellowship

Recent Professional Experience

OBELISK GLOBAL FUNDS – Sao Paulo – SP

Dec/2016 – Current

A start-up corporation providing financing for small and medium enterprises in Brazil and other emerging markets

Director

Accomplishments:

- Have supported the setting up of several funds in Brazil and abroad
- Have analyzed investment opportunities in emerging markets
- Have introduced opportunities existing in emerging markets to international investors

FAAP – São Paulo, SP – SP

Feb/2007 - Current

A private University with more than 5,000 students

Professor of Law and International Relations

Accomplishments:

- Have taught classes at the undergraduate, graduate and MBA programs
- Coordinated the International Relations Program (2012-2013), implementing a new curriculum leading to an increase of course visibility at the internal and external levels and enhanced employability of students
- Have ministered lectures and courses in the following countries: United States, United Kingdom, Belgium, France, China, Canada and Japan

Courses and Expertise

Several courses on strategic thought and planning in Brazil and abroad

- Deep knowledge of International Economics and Politics acquired in several think tanks, international organizations and universities in Brazil and throughout the world

Areas of Interest and Other Information

Volunteer work in political and religious organizations

- History, horseback riding, and swimming
- Senior Non-Resident Fellow, OCP Policy Center, in Rabat, Morocco
- Best Professor in the years 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012 and 2013
- Special Guest of the Governments of Canada (2014) and Japan (2016) to promote closer ties with Brazil
- Honor Recognition by the Sao Paulo City Council (2010)
- More than 700 interviews given on International Politics and Economics to Brazilian and international media outlets

Appendix E: Letters of Recommendation

June 20, 1999

To Whom it may concern,

Dr. Maria Helena Fonseca de Souza Rolim has worked with me on many occasions over the past two years as the legal consultant for INPE on issues concerning the International Space Station (ISS) Program. In October 1997, Dr. Maria Helena, traveled to the United States to research international Space Law in regards to ISS and discuss certain aspects of the agreement for participation in ISS between the two countries. During this visit in Houston, Tx., she was introduced to and discussed ISS with several JSC organizations including the International Partners Office, ISS, the JSC Legal Office, and the ISS contracts office.

Since my arrival in Brazil, June, 1998, as the NASA ISS Representative in Brazil I have regularly met with Dr. Maria Helena to discuss various aspects of space law and the agreement between our two countries. I have worked with her in coordinating review and construction of documents for ISS.

In all of my contact and work with Dr. Maria Helena, I have found her work to be very thorough and professional. Her depth of knowledge and expertise in the area of space law is broadly recognized.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Mark R. Hershey".

Mark R. Hershey
NASA Representative in Brazil
International Space Station Program

